

Youth in war: psychological experiences, migration plans, self-realization

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ABSTRACT

The scientific article is dedicated to studying the impact of the full-scale invasion on the youth of Ukraine, specifically synthesizing the psychological experience of war among youth both in Ukraine and abroad. Based on nationwide sociological surveys conducted in 2023, opinions have been formed regarding the migration plans of youth, volunteering intentions, and visions of personal and career self-realization. This study utilizes secondary analysis of data from sociological research conducted by Kantar, the analytical center Cedos, and the research agency "Info Sapiens." The article provides suggestions and practical recommendations for engaging Ukrainian youth in the process of Ukraine's recovery and facilitating its adaptation to the new challenges of the post-war period. Fundamental and emotionally charged aspects of the war's impact on young people are identified, and innovative approaches are developed to improve the current state of interaction between the state and youth. Attention is drawn to the necessity of creating favorable conditions by the state to stimulate employers to hire young people, implementing programs for paid internships and professional mentoring with opportunities for further employment, simplifying the financing and taxation system for youth businesses, as well as creating a program to incentivize the return of youth who left Ukraine due to the war.

KEYWORDS

*youth,
full-scale war,
self-realization,
migration sentiments,
future plans,
uncertainty*

Introduction

Under the influence of geopolitical turbulences and military wars, youth becomes a vulnerable group, witnessing and participating in military events that leave indelible marks on their mental health and can disrupt the plans of the younger generation for the future. In times of war, the factor of uncertainty grows significantly, exerting a substantial influence on the life strategy of the youth, unlike in peacetime when individuals can make plans for the future.

The subject of this scientific article is the study of the existential parameters of the human life of young people in wartime, their migratory attitudes, opportunities for self-realization in personal and career contexts. Researching these aspects is an important task, as young people form a collective vision of the future in conditions of uncertainty.

The situation in Ukraine over the past few years has deepened the sense of future uncertainty, thereby complicating the process of life orientation for young people, as well as their professional realization.

One of the key aspects explored in this work is the migration plans of youth under the influence of wartime. Choosing to stay in Ukraine and cope with difficulties or seeking new opportunities abroad becomes a difficult decision, determined not only by economic prospects but also by the desire to find security and stability in a turbulent world.

The opportunity and willingness to participate in various volunteer initiatives enable young people to demonstrate their activism and make a significant contribution to

Ukraine's victory in the war. At the same time, this can serve as a mechanism for psychological support and the formation of internal identity.

Furthermore, this study delves into the question of shaping one's self-realization in personal and career contexts. The turbulent present challenges conventional paths of professional and personal development and necessitates finding adaptive ways to achieve one's goals.

This article also provides practical recommendations for state policies regarding the integration of youth into Ukraine's labor market and creating favorable conditions for the return of young people who left due to the war.

The life strategies of youth are the subject of study by such Ukrainian scholars as A.A. Bova, V.F. Baranivskiy, Yu.V. Zablotska, V.V. Kryvoshein, A.O. Belenok, V.V. Nikolenko, and Yu.O. Chaliuk. The moods of youth during wartime have been investigated within the framework of nationwide sociological studies such as "Adolescents and their lives during wartime: moods, values, future," conducted by the company Kantar; "The impact of war on the youth of Ukraine," conducted by the analytical center Cedos and the research agency "Info Sapiens."

The aim of this scientific article is to conduct a secondary analysis of sociological research and gain a deep understanding of the impact of wartime on the psychological state of youth in Ukraine and abroad, assess their migration attitudes, identify paths of self-realization on personal

and professional levels, and provide proposals and recommendations regarding the process of engaging and repatriating youth to Ukraine.

Research methods

The methodology employed in this study aimed to comprehensively examine the impact of a year of full-scale invasion on the youth of Ukraine, with a specific focus on their psychological experiences of war, migration plans, desire to volunteer, and visions of self-realization in personal and career aspects. To achieve this objective, a secondary analysis of data from multiple sociological studies conducted by reputable agencies was conducted.

The primary sources of data utilized in this research were the findings from studies such as "Teenagers and their life during the war: attitudes, values, future" conducted by the sociological company Kantar Ukraine in March 2023, which consisted of two stages - quantitative, where there were 600 respondents aged 13-19 were interviewed and qualitative, where 4 focus groups were held with teenagers aged 13-19; "The impact of the war on the youth of Ukraine" conducted by the analytical center Cedos and the research agency "Info Sapiens" in October 2022 - January 2023, which consisted of two quantitative stages, where 2064 respondents aged 14-34 were interviewed in the controlled territories of Ukraine and 405 young of people aged 14-34 years who went abroad and a qualitative one - during which 12 focus groups were conducted with young people aged 14-34 years. These studies were chosen due to the comprehensive coverage of the opinions and attitudes of Ukrainian youth towards various aspects of the impact of the war. In particular, the data analyzed included perceptions of the uncertainty of the future, problems in making personal plans, migration attitudes, and perceptions of self-fulfillment during wartime.

The main researched aspects that were described in this scientific work focused on the following questions, namely, what worries young people now, the impact of uncertainty on the construction of life plans by young people, and the study of the phenomenon of volunteering among young people. As for methodological limitations, it should be noted that in the study "Teenagers and their life during the war: attitudes, values, future", young people were not interviewed in full, as only young people aged 13 to 19 were interviewed. On the other hand, this limitation in the sample does not diminish the significance of these results for this scientific work.

The secondary analysis of these datasets involved a rigorous examination of quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the experiences and perspectives of young individuals affected by the war. Statistical techniques were employed to identify patterns, trends, and correlations within the data, while qualitative analysis methods facilitated a deeper exploration of individual narratives and lived experiences.

Furthermore, the research methodology incorporated a comparative analysis approach, enabling the examination of differences and similarities in the experiences of youth both within Ukraine and those residing abroad. By considering the perspectives of diverse groups of young people, this study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted impact of war on youth across different contexts.

Results and Discussion

War brings destruction not only to military objects but also to civilian infrastructure, disrupts people's lives, and

alters life plans. Psychological tension and stress are responses of the organism to extreme conditions, extraordinary situations that arise during wartime. Hans Selye (1956) outlined three stages of stress development:

1) Alarm, which includes phases of shock and counter-shock, allowing individuals to mobilize their forces for fighting or fleeing from danger.

2) Adaptation, where the individual's resistance to trials and negative factors increases.

3) Exhaustion, which involves the disruption of self-regulation mechanisms.

During such psychological upheaval as war, it's impossible to avoid stressors that negatively impact a person's psychological state. However, stress not only has negative effects but also can have positive ones, such as aiding survival in adverse conditions and adapting to a new turbulent reality.

The most significant stressors for youth include: bombings and shelling; panic among adults; curfews and restrictions during wartime; sirens; various sabotage actions and terrorist attacks; destruction of residential buildings; information about captives, mass violence, torture, losses; the necessity of staying in bomb shelters. Such varieties are distinguished in their works by O. Radchenko (2022) and K. Zhurba (2022).

UN specialists consider youth as one of the most vulnerable population groups. Restrictions on movement, the transition of educational institutions to remote learning, have impacted the mental health of young people. Youth who are neither in education nor employed constitute a particularly high-risk group prone to marginalization, alienation, poverty, and social exclusion. The term NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) has been widely used for 10-15 years in strategic documents of international organizations such as the EU, OECD, ILO, UNICEF, and the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA). Today, there are approximately 1.3 billion young people in the world, of whom 267 million belong to the NEET group. According to UN statistics from 2020, one in five young people aged 15 to 24 worldwide is a member of the NEET group. The world is concerned about such a high number of young people who are not seeking employment, not pursuing education, and not aiming to improve their professional qualifications (Kyrylenko, Chaliuk, 2022).

That's why reducing the number of NEET youth is part of the Sustainable Development Agenda for 2030. The most common problems faced by NEET youth include high food prices, low income levels, unemployment, and employment-related issues, high cost of higher education, and lack of housing. The reasons hindering permanent employment include low wages, lack of experience, and job opportunities at the place of residence. As for the reasons for youth entering the NEET category, the following are highlighted:

- Individual factors: low education level and poor quality of education, health condition (physical and mental health, drug addiction, alcoholism, substance abuse), negative experience of teenage pregnancy and early childbirth.

- Family factors: unemployed parents or parents with low education levels, large families, low household income levels, poor living conditions, living in small or remote settlements.

- Social factors (socialization factors): limitations or deprivation of opportunities for social inclusion in low-income families.

- Factors that increase the likelihood of entering the NEET group: presence of migrant status among young people; belonging to racial and ethnic minorities.

- Deformation of the traditional value system: loss of the primary value of work and its replacement with paternalistic expectations or dependency attitudes (Kyrylenko, Chaliuk, 2022).

Among the risk factors identified by scientists are the following:

- Education: Youth with a low level of education are three times more likely to become NEET.
- Immigration: Youth with an immigration background have a 70% higher chance of becoming NEET compared to resident citizens.
- Disability: Youth suffering from disabilities have a 40% higher likelihood of becoming NEET.
- Parental unemployment: The presence of unemployed parents increases the likelihood of youth becoming NEET by 17%.
- Household income: Youth with low income levels are much more likely to become NEET compared to other layers of the population.
- Location: Residing in remote areas increases the likelihood of becoming NEET by 1.5 times.
- Parental divorce: Youth who have experienced parental divorce have a 30% higher chance of becoming NEET (Kyrylenko, Chaliuk, 2022)

In summary, it should be noted that the majority of the NEET generation are individuals with somewhat hedonistic life positions and consumer-oriented philosophies, regardless of the country of residence. For Ukraine, the phenomenon of NEET youth is a relatively new social phenomenon and an interdisciplinary research direction. The prevalence of this phenomenon and life philosophy among Ukrainian youth could quickly lead to socio-economic and political destabilization in our country.

Worries of youth

Based on the nationwide sociological research conducted by Kantar, as of March 2023, the greatest concern for youth is the war (73%). Compared to life during the pandemic, life in wartime has transformed the plans and life strategies of 87% of the surveyed young people. 38% of youth are concerned about their own lives and the health of their loved ones. 12% feel uncertain about the future, 10% are compelled to relocate to their friends in other countries/cities, and 5% face the absence of electricity/internet/communication (Adolescents and their lives..., 2023).

The sociological study by Info Sapiens, "The Impact of War on the Youth of Ukraine" (October 2022 - January 2023), demonstrates similar experiences among youth regarding their health both abroad and in Ukraine. However, youth who have emigrated abroad are significantly more likely to encounter psychological problems, lack of money, and job opportunities. They also feel changes in the relevance of their profession, likely due to emigration. Youth who have not emigrated abroad experience material needs (electricity, security, money), while for those who have emigrated abroad, non-material needs come to the forefront (psychological well-being, self-realization, the need for communication). For youth who have emigrated abroad, the main problems include: 54% - mental health (poor mood, feeling down, depression, anxiety); 47% - health (their own and their loved ones); 33% - lack of opportunities for self-realization, self-development; 27% - lack of friends, difficulties in communicating with others (Impact of war on youth in Ukraine, 2023).

The level of resilience depends on the individual's ability to accurately assess the situation and find solutions in extraordinary circumstances. The development of resilience should be directed towards:

- Planning and organizing one's life and achieving life goals;
- Taking into account the survival experience of past generations in wartime conditions;
- Creating one's own experience of overcoming difficulties.

During wartime, young people often experience acute emotional reactions to what is happening: excessive arousal, fear, mood swings, hysterics, and so on. In young individuals who are far from the combat zone (relatively safe), feelings of guilt (survivor guilt) may develop. Conversely, under the influence of sharp dramatic events, the ability to empathize (derealization) may be lost as a protective mental reaction. Considering all of this, emotional resilience helps individuals cope with negative experiences and feelings, allowing them to adapt more quickly to new realities and perceive difficulties as temporary. Additionally, emotional resilience is also defined as the ability to make decisions in serious life situations. Using the research by K. Zhurba (2022), I have compiled Table 1, which provides a general classification of components of the emotional stability of an individual and the method of their normalization.

Table 1. Components of emotional stability

Physical characteristics	Psychological characteristics	Moral characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health • Energy • Endurance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-esteem • Self-regulation • Attention • Purposefulness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Love • Partnership • Identity
<p>Increasing the level of emotional stability can be carried out at the expense of personal self-awareness, willpower, critical thinking, determination and persistence, interpersonal relations and communications.</p>		

According to the survey "Adolescents and Their Lives," the main aspirations of adolescents include being strong

and resilient (14%), psychologically and morally resilient (14%), believing in oneself and being self-confident (14%),

not losing heart (14%), and not panicking, maintaining calmness (12%) (*Adolescents and their lives...*, 2023).

Youth Plans and the Impact of Uncertainty

According to the nationwide sociological study "Adolescents and Their Lives," nearly half of the youth have been influenced in their perception of their own future, and for most, it has become difficult to make plans. For 87%, it has become challenging to plan anything for the long term due to the war, and for 47% of the youth, the war has changed their perception of their own future. However, 67% know what they want to become in the future (*Adolescents and their lives...*, 2023).

According to the aforementioned study, even the youth who choose to stay in Ukraine are consciously making this choice. Even the portion of adolescents planning to study abroad due to the unpredictability and uncertainty of the situation in Ukraine express readiness to return to Ukraine.

Regarding the migration plans of the youth, according to the study "The Impact of War on the Youth of Ukraine," the proportion of young people who do not plan to leave their place of residence increased from 48% in 2022 to 66% in 2023 (*Impact of war on youth in Ukraine, 2023*). This may be explained by the return of some youth from abroad or other populated areas (16% became disillusioned with migration and decided to stay in their place of residence due to a sense of social cohesion and patriotism). By age groups, there is a tendency for younger individuals to be more inclined to leave their place of residence, which decreases among older groups accordingly. Participants in focus groups in the Info Sapiens study who do not plan to leave Ukraine due to the war cited the following reasons for their decision: lack of funds, the need to learn the language of another country, unwillingness to leave their job and live anywhere except Ukraine, as well as fear of the difficulty of finding specialist doctors abroad who could oversee their health. Conversely, young people considering leaving the country explained their decision by the power outages, which complicate the work and life of Ukrainians. Among other reasons, they mentioned the possibility of a repeat invasion of Russian troops into Ukraine. Participants in focus groups who plan to return after the war ends stated that possible motives for their return would be the end of the war. In addition, participants cited such decisive factors as demining territories, the Ukrainian government's restoration of control over their region, and international partners' investment in their city. Some plan to return no earlier than 2 years or after the full reconstruction of infrastructure, or they will wait for a change in Russia's political leadership.

Regarding the life goals, according to the survey "The Impact of War on the Youth of Ukraine," (2023) the top three priorities for young people are family happiness (71%), health (62%), and career (56%). An interesting aspect is that for young people abroad, in addition to family happiness and health, freedom entered the top 3 most important goals (60%), and in fourth place was benefit for their country (57%). Overall, young people abroad less frequently mentioned material goals (wealth, career), which may be due to their more satisfied material needs.

The perception of promising and attractive professions in terms of life success remains unchanged since 2021 – business and enterprise and IT. Military professions rank third in terms of providing success, with 23% considering them as such, compared to 11% in the past. Today, an increasing number of young people find the field of trade attractive: 16% in 2023 compared to 11% in 2021. This could

be attributed to the fact that after the start of full-scale invasion, 25.1% of new individual entrepreneurs opened businesses in the retail trade sector. The popularity of jurisprudence, design, banking, and pedagogy has decreased (*Impact of war on youth in Ukraine, 2023*).

According to the nationwide survey "Adolescents and Their Lives," (2023) 48% of young people associate their hobbies and preferences with self-realization. Of those, 85% have their own hobbies: sports (17%), music (16%), web design (13%), visual arts (13%), dance (11%). As for adolescents' understanding of the concept of "self-realization," 29% see it as achieving set goals; for 24%, it's understanding their goals; 20% enjoy engaging in their favorite activity; another 20% strive to improve in their favorite activity or hobby; and 20% focus on developing their abilities and potential. Most young people believe they are making efforts towards self-realization (90%), with 38% trying to excel academically and acquire knowledge, 35% watching/listening to lectures on YouTube, 18% studying a foreign language with a tutor, and 18% attending courses/extracurricular activities on non-school subjects. Young people hardly feel that the external consequences of war directly block their self-realization. Among the obstacles on the path to self-realization, young people point out such external factors as the lack of electricity (28%) and poor or no internet, necessary for accessing resources (12%). Among the internal factors that adolescents complain about are laziness (23%), insufficient motivation, lack of willpower (11%), and inability to plan time properly (11%) (*Adolescents and their lives...*, 2023).

Youth and Volunteering.

After the start of full-scale invasion, the number of young people involved in volunteering increased, according to the study "The Impact of War on the Youth of Ukraine" (2023). A third joined the volunteer movement amidst the full-scale invasion, while another 13% had been volunteering in 2021 and continued to do so in 2022. Comparing the situations before and after February 24th, the most noticeable change is the increase in the proportion of conscious young people who joined the volunteer movement. In 2021, the share of young people who first joined volunteering in the last 12 months was 6%, while in 2022, it increased to 30% (*Impact of war on youth in Ukraine, 2023*).

Most young people were involved in fundraising for the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AFU) or aspire to join such efforts in the future. Common forms of youth volunteering include fundraising, organizing and collecting humanitarian aid, as well as providing physical assistance on-site, aiding soldiers, refugees, and internally displaced persons (IDPs).

Comparing with 2021, young people now more often engage in volunteering out of personal initiative (43%), with almost every third person doing so through friends or acquaintances (27%).

Regarding motivations for volunteering, there is a desire to help specific individuals (34%), contribute to society (32%), as well as a desire to join a collective cause (27%) and direct motivation due to the onset of full-scale invasion (22%).

According to the "Adolescents and Their Lives" survey, 43% of adolescents have already participated in volunteering activities during the full-scale war. Among them, half collected funds for the AFU (49%), 35% made camouflage nets, 28% helped children with clothing and toys, 27% assisted in packing aid, and 20% prepared and distributed

food. Additionally, the survey asked young people, "If you had a million dollars, what would you spend it on?" The results showed that 36% of young people would spend it on supporting the Armed Forces of Ukraine, 24% would help their families, and 23% would donate the funds to charitable initiatives (*Impact of war on youth in Ukraine, 2023*).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is evident that young people are undergoing a reevaluation of values and life priorities due to the war. The war has changed the youth, making them value every moment of life more, become more decisive about their future career paths and aspirations. The experience of war has instilled in them a heightened appreciation for life's moments and a greater sense of determination in shaping their futures. Furthermore, the prevailing patriotic sentiment among the youth underscores their resilience and commitment to their homeland. Currently, the youth are in a patriotic and resilient mood, as evidenced by the majority's desire to remain in Ukraine or return to it if they have left or plan to leave.

The war has affected the youth in various ways. Young people are increasingly concerned about their physical and mental health, financial constraints, and the lack of opportunities for employment and self-realization. Therefore, it is imperative for the government to start developing a recovery plan, with special attention to educational and economic initiatives, as well as modernizing the healthcare sector. The war has affected the youth in various ways. Young people are increasingly concerned about their physical and mental health, financial constraints, and the lack of opportunities for employment and self-realization. Therefore, it is imperative for the government to start developing a recovery plan, with special attention to educational and economic initiatives, as well as modernizing the healthcare sector. As such, it is incumbent upon the government to initiate a comprehensive recovery plan tailored to address these pressing concerns. First and foremost, prioritizing investment in the healthcare sector is essential to meet the increased demand for mental health services and trauma care. The psychological toll of war on young minds cannot be understated, and therefore, expanding access to counseling, therapy, and support networks is paramount. Additionally, efforts to modernize healthcare infrastructure and improve the quality of medical services will contribute to the overall resilience and well-being of the youth population.

In devising and implementing this recovery plan, collaboration between government agencies, civil society organizations, and international partners is indispensable. By harnessing collective expertise and resources, we can ensure a holistic and sustainable approach to rebuilding the lives and futures of Ukraine's youth. On a positive note, the full-scale invasion by Russia has led to an increase in youth civic engagement. Hence, it is now pertinent to consider involving young people in the process of rebuilding political and civic activities. Regarding information dissemination to the youth, it is essential to utilize the social media platforms most popular among adolescents. According to the Cedos survey, these platforms include Telegram (73%), YouTube (54%), and Instagram (47%).

Given this, stakeholders involved in addressing youth policy issues, governmental bodies, and youth organiza-

tions should utilize not only official communication channels (such as websites) but also collaborate with popular social media platforms among young people.

Nearly every fifth young person is concerned about the lack of opportunities for self-realization and the inability to find employment. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a program to support the return of youth to the labor market and their professional development: assistance in finding new jobs or starting their own businesses, help with retraining, especially for those who lost their jobs due to forced internal migration. Regarding the formats of support, it could include:

- Encouraging employers to hire young people;
- Establishing infrastructure for consulting young entrepreneurs on legal, economic, and tax issues;
- Simplifying the conditions for financing youth businesses;
- Developing programs for professional mentorship and paid internships.

The most important task for the government is to bring youth back to the country. According to the Cedos study, 76% of young people who left abroad due to the war aspire to return to Ukraine. Therefore, the development of a program by the government with official calls for youth to return can have a significant effect. This program may include the following directions:

- Meeting basic needs (rebuilding housing and infrastructure, access to quality education and healthcare, creating jobs with high salaries);
- Information and communication work (effective communication with Ukrainians abroad and recipient countries);
- Implementation of incentives (grant programs, assistance in job placement, compensation for return costs, access to housing).

Continuing the narrative, the imperative of bringing young Ukrainians back to their homeland underscores the urgency of implementing targeted policies and programs aimed at facilitating their return and reintegration. Recognizing the strong desire of 76% of young expatriates to return to Ukraine, the government must seize this opportunity to harness their potential and rebuild the nation.

Central to this effort is the development of a comprehensive repatriation program that addresses the multifaceted needs of returning youth. Firstly, ensuring access to basic necessities such as housing, infrastructure, education, and healthcare is paramount. This may involve initiatives to rebuild war-torn communities, expand educational opportunities, and enhance healthcare services to meet the needs of returning residents.

Furthermore, effective communication and outreach efforts are essential to engage with Ukrainians abroad and facilitate their return. By fostering channels of communication with expatriates and recipient countries, the government can provide accurate information, address concerns, and streamline the repatriation process. Utilizing digital platforms and social media channels can enhance outreach efforts and foster a sense of belonging among the diaspora.

Incentivizing return migration through the implementation of targeted incentives is also critical to encourage young Ukrainians to come back home. This may include grant programs to support entrepreneurship and job creation, assistance in job placement, and financial compensation to offset the costs associated with relocation. Additionally, providing access to affordable housing and support

services can alleviate the challenges of resettlement and facilitate smooth reintegration into Ukrainian society.

By prioritizing the repatriation and reintegration of young Ukrainians, the government can tap into a valuable resource of talent, skills, and expertise essential for the nation's recovery and development. Moreover, fostering a sense of belonging and opportunity among returning youth is instrumental in building a brighter and more prosperous future for Ukraine.

Findings of this research have practical implications for policymakers, stakeholders, and practitioners involved in youth development and post-war reconstruction efforts. The proposals and practical recommendations derived from the study aim to engage Ukrainian youth in the process of Ukraine's recovery and facilitate their adaptation to the new challenges of the post-war period.

This study contributes to the existing literature by acknowledging the fundamental and emotionally charged aspects of the wartime impact on young individuals. Moreover, it offers innovative approaches to enhance the current state of interaction between the state and youth. Specifically, the proposed interventions include creating favorable conditions by the government to incentivize employers to hire young people, establishing programs for paid internships and professional mentorship with the opportunity for subsequent employment, simplifying the system of youth business financing and taxation, as well as creating programs to encourage the return of young people who left Ukraine due to the war back to the country.

In summary, the methodology employed in this study enabled a comprehensive exploration of the impact of war on Ukrainian youth, providing valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners seeking to support young people

affected by war and facilitate their integration into post-war society.

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Молодь на війні: психологічний досвід, міграційні плани, самореалізація

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Наукова стаття присвячена дослідженню впливу повномасштабного вторгнення на молодь України, зокрема узагальнюється психологічний досвід війни серед молоді як в Україні, так і за кордоном. На підставі всеукраїнських соціологічних опитувань 2023 року сформовано думку про міграційні плани молоді, намірів волонтерства та бачення самореалізації в особистісному та кар'єрному аспектах. У цьому дослідженні використано вторинний аналіз даних соціологічних досліджень, проведених Kantar, аналітичним центром Cedos та дослідницьким агентством «Info Sapiens». У статті подано пропозиції та практичні рекомендації щодо залучення української молоді до процесу відновлення України та сприяння її адаптації до нових викликів повоєнного періоду. Визначено фундаментальні та емоційно заряджені аспекти впливу війни на молодих людей, розроблено інноваційні підходи для покращення сучасного стану взаємодії держави та молоді. Акцентовано увагу на необхідності створення державою сприятливих умов для стимулювання роботодавців до працевлаштування молоді, запровадження програм оплачуваного стажування та професійного наставництва з можливістю подальшого працевлаштування, спрощення системи фінансування та оподаткування молодіжного бізнесу, а також створення програми для заохочення повернення в країну молоді, яка покинула Україну через війну.

Ключові слова: молодь, повномасштабна війна, самореалізація, міграційні настрої, плани на майбутнє, невідзначеність.

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